
**A STUDY ON LIFESTYLE OF SIDDI TRIBAL COMMUNITY
RESIDING IN ARBAILVILLAGE OF UTTARA KANNADA.**

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Abstract:

This paper includes a crisp about tribal community (Siddhi) residing in Arbail village. It speaks about the living of tribal community in Arbail village. Their belief, customs, lifestyle etc. The Siddis hail from Africa. History says that they were ferried to Goa as slaves. The community first settled in Goa and eventually migrated to Karnataka in search of food and shelter, but were not met with better fate when they arrived. Siddis live in India, mostly they cover Yellapur, Haliyal, Ankola, Joida, Mundgod, Sirsi and other parts of Uttara Kannada. They adopt a healthy living like us. They usually dress in traditional Indian clothes, and naturally they mingle with other locals. Although Siddis primarily speak Konkani (local dialect), they speak Kannada too. The official language of the state fluently. Although many Indians might view the Siddi people as being out of place because of their physical African characteristics. Most families live in small villages, isolated groups, or individual households in the forests farther away and must travel to the larger towns once a week on specific market days to purchase groceries. Even in the field of education, they go to school, colleges etc. Farming is their main occupation. Furthermore, many points are dealt in this paper.

Keywords: Lifestyle, Occupation, Education , Religion, Population.

Lifestyle:

Siddi culture is not rigid or uniform: they speak various languages such as Konkani, Kannada, Hindi, Urdu and Gujarati, and are known to practise Islam, Hinduism as well as Christianity. Siddi communities, although classified as a tribe by the Indian government, primarily live in agricultural communities where men are responsible for the farming and women are responsible for the home and focus on other family members. Outside of their communities, men also tend to be employed as farmers, drivers, manual labourers, and security guards.

Occupation:

The Siddi women are resilient and intelligent, using their skills to earn an income. primarily live in agricultural communities where men are responsible for the farming and women are responsible for the home and focus on other family members. Outside of their communities, men also tend to be employed as farmers, drivers, manual labourers, and security guards. They sew and sow, ride scooters and insist their children go to school, and the men go out and find paying work.

Education:

Many Siddi children must travel a long distance every day to attend school. Even if a Siddi village has a school, it is commonly just for younger children. Older Siddi children often end up going to boarding schools in larger towns if they can get assistance from the government. Even if an opportunity exists for Siddi children who live near larger towns to go to school. fortunately government of Karnataka has provide various facilities to the students so that they gain more knowledge and skill at the same time.

Religion:

Most of the Siddis of Arvail follow Hinduism, Christianity and Islam. They are religious and follow their beliefs and tradition. Most Christian Siddis are Catholic and were probably converted/baptized to Christianity after being brought to India by the Portuguese. The greater Catholic Church sends non-Siddi priests into the smaller villages to conduct Sunday services. Christian Siddi communities often have better educational outcomes due to the involvement and financial support of church groups, which have set up schools and other facilities. They opt for different religions, they intermarry across religions without reservations. One element that wraps them irrespective of their religion is worshipping their ancestor.

Population:

The Siddis, who hailed from different parts of Africa, have converted into a single tribe over the years. Although Siddi tribe has cover a vast part of India or Karnataka. The population Siddis in Arvail Village is approximately hundred in number. They live in a nuclear as well as in a joint family. They give more priorities to their relatives ,children. They celebrate normal festivals according to their religion and just get together.

Conclusion:

Siddi tribes started living in India long ago, they opt everything according to the place they live. Very few people know about them. Earlier they had poverty in the family but, in this present scenario most of the tribes are well educated and working for their future. They work as labourers in field or any Brahmins house to do household chores.

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